

Figure S5: Structural variations and large deletions found in a duplication event surrounding the target 1 of PDS-1-118. Mates of blue reads have the same strand orientation and their insert sizes have a length of 2kb, as expected of an inversion event associated to a larger deletion event. Two large deletions of 4.6 Kb (red reads) and another one of 2,4 Kb (orange reads) can also be found. A small deletion of 5bp is also shown (green reads). The sequencing depth as number of reads is shown in blue.

